

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

Low circulating valine associate with high risk of hip fractures

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SUPPLEMENTAL TABLES

Supplemental Table 1. List of ICD 10 and ICD 9 codes used to identify fracture cases

Fracture type	ICD 10	ICD 9
Any	S02, S12, S22, S32, S42, S52, S62, S72, S82, S92	80, 81, 82
Forearm	S52	8130, 8131, 8132, 8133, 8134, 8135, 8138, 8139
Major osteoporotic	S22.0, S22.1, S32.0, S42.2, S52.5, S52.6, S72.0, S72.1, S72.2	8120, 8121, 8052, 8053, 8062, 8063, 8054, 8055, 8064, 8065, 8134, 8135, 8200, 8201, 8202, 8203, 8208, 8209
Hip	S72.0, S72.1, S72.2	8200, 8201, 8202, 8203, 8208, 8209

Supplemental Table 2. Amino acid analyses in the UK Biobank

Cohort	Amino acid	Number of samples			
		Number of samples	Below LOQ	Failure in assay	Included in analyses
UK Biobank - full dataset	Alanine	117,425	0	1	117,424
	Glutamine	117,425	0	352	117,073
	Glycine	117,425	42	104	117,321
	Histidine	117,425	0	214	117,211
	Isoleucine	117,425	0	0	117,425
	Leucine	117,425	0	1	117,424
	Valine	117,425	0	28	117,397
	Phenylalanine	117,425	0	74	117,351
	Tyrosine	117,425	1	195	117,230
UK Biobank - whites	Alanine	111,257	0	1	111,256
	Glutamine	111,257	0	328	110,929
	Glycine	111,257	40	97	111,160
	Histidine	111,257	0	203	111,054
	Isoleucine	111,257	0	0	111,257
	Leucine	111,257	0	1	111,256
	Valine	111,257	0	27	111,230
	Phenylalanine	111,257	0	69	111,188
	Tyrosine	111,257	0	187	111,070

LOQ = Limit of quantification

Supplemental Table 3. Characteristics of UK Biobank study subjects

	UK Biobank, whites N=111,257
Age, years (SD)	56.7 (8.0)
Women, N (%)	60,311 (54.2)
BMI, kg/m ² (SD)	27.4 (4.8)
Fasting time, hours (SD)	3.8 (2.4)
eBMD, g/cm ² (SD)	0.54 (0.1)

Values are given as mean (standard deviation, SD) or N (%). BMI = body mass index, eBMD = estimated bone mineral density

Supplemental Table 4. Associations between amino acid levels and different fracture types in the UK Biobank cohort

	Any fractures				Hip fractures				Forearm fracture				MOF				N
	HR	95% CI)	p-value	fractures	HR	95% CI)	p-value	fractures	HR	95% CI)	p-value	fractures	HR	95% CI)	p-value	fractures	
Valine	0.89	(0.87, 0.91)	5.5×10^{-18}	5724	0.79	(0.73, 0.84)	2.5×10^{-12}	901	0.88	(0.83, 0.92)	5.2×10^{-7}	1483	0.83	(0.80, 0.86)	2.5×10^{-20}	2659	111,230
Leucine	0.91	(0.88, 0.93)	3.7×10^{-13}	5725	0.81	(0.76, 0.86)	2.2×10^{-10}	901	0.91	(0.87, 0.96)	7.0×10^{-4}	1483	0.86	(0.83, 0.90)	1.3×10^{-13}	2660	111,256
Alanine	0.94	(0.92, 0.96)	3.2×10^{-6}	5725	0.90	(0.84, 0.96)	1.8×10^{-3}	901	0.90	(0.86, 0.95)	6.4×10^{-5}	1483	0.90	(0.86, 0.93)	2.2×10^{-8}	2660	111,256
Isoleucine	0.94	(0.92, 0.97)	4.4×10^{-6}	5725	0.86	(0.80, 0.92)	8.7×10^{-6}	901	0.94	(0.90, 0.99)	2.9×10^{-2}	1483	0.91	(0.87, 0.94)	5.5×10^{-7}	2660	111,257
Histidine	0.96	(0.93, 0.98)	1.3×10^{-3}	5710	0.89	(0.83, 0.95)	3.1×10^{-4}	897	0.99	(0.94, 1.04)	7.1×10^{-1}	1480	0.95	(0.92, 0.99)	1.1×10^{-2}	2654	111,054
Tyrosine	0.96	(0.93, 0.99)	2.3×10^{-3}	5712	0.90	(0.84, 0.96)	2.6×10^{-3}	898	0.98	(0.93, 1.03)	4.6×10^{-1}	1481	0.94	(0.91, 0.98)	3.6×10^{-3}	2656	111,070
Phenylalanine	0.97	(0.94, 0.99)	1.1×10^{-2}	5719	0.95	(0.88, 1.01)	9.5×10^{-2}	899	0.94	(0.89, 0.99)	1.4×10^{-2}	1483	0.95	(0.91, 0.98)	4.5×10^{-3}	2658	111,188
Glutamine	0.98	(0.95, 1.00)	9.9×10^{-2}	5699	0.98	(0.92, 1.05)	5.9×10^{-1}	897	1.05	(1.00, 1.11)	5.3×10^{-2}	1480	0.99	(0.95, 1.03)	7.0×10^{-1}	2648	110,929
Glycine	1.01	(0.99, 1.04)	3.5×10^{-1}	5721	1.06	(0.98, 1.14)	1.2×10^{-1}	898	1.07	(1.00, 1.13)	3.4×10^{-2}	1483	1.05	(1.00, 1.09)	3.6×10^{-2}	2656	111,160

Cox proportional hazards regression models adjusted for age, sex, fasting time, and UK Biobank assessment center. Hazard ratios (HR) are given with 95% confidence intervals (CI) and expressed per standard deviation increase in ln transformed amino acid level. MOF = major osteoporotic fractures

Supplemental Table 5. Associations between amino acids and eBMD in the UK Biobank cohort

	β	95% CI	p-value	N
Valine	0.043	(0.037, 0.048)	1.1×10^{-47}	108,548
Leucine	0.038	(0.033, 0.044)	4.0×10^{-39}	108,572
Alanine	0.031	(0.025, 0.037)	4.0×10^{-26}	108,572
Isoleucine	0.013	(0.007, 0.018)	1.7×10^{-5}	108,573
Histidine	0.007	(0.001, 0.013)	1.9×10^{-2}	108,380
Tyrosine	0.002	(-0.004, 0.008)	5.4×10^{-1}	108,396
Phenylalanine	0.000	(-0.005, 0.006)	9.0×10^{-1}	108,508
Glutamine	-0.025	(-0.031, -0.020)	6.3×10^{-18}	108,258
Glycine	-0.031	(-0.036, -0.025)	1.8×10^{-25}	108,480

Linear regression models adjusted for age, sex, fasting time, and UK Biobank assessment center. Beta values are given with 95% confidence intervals (CI) and expressed as standard deviation per standard deviation increase in ln transformed amino acid level.

Supplemental Table 6. Characteristics of the UFO hip fracture case/control study

	All N=4,450	Cases N=2,225	Controls N=2,225
Age baseline, years (SD)	58.8 (7.1)	58.8 (7.1)	58.8 (7.0)
Follow-up time, years (SD)	13.9 (6.9)	13.9 (6.9)	13.9 (6.9)
Women, N (%)	3188 (71.6)	1594 (71.6)	1594 (71.6)
Fasting Yes, N (%)	3236 (72.7)	1618 (72.7)	1618 (72.7)

Values are given as means (standard deviation, SD) or N (%)

Supplemental Table 7. Descriptive data of the HR-pQCT analyses in the tibia in the MrOS Sweden cohort

	N	
Males, N (%)	449	449 (100)
Age (years)	449	80.2 (3.5)
BMI (kg/m ²)	449	25.9 (3.2)
Current smokers, N (%)	449	19 (4.2)
Cortical area (mm ²)	449	120 (35)
Cortical vBMD (mg/cm ³)	448	805 (81)
Cortical porosity (%)	449	11.8 (4.1)
Trabecular vBMD (mg/cm ³)	449	179 (34)
Trabecular number (mm ⁻¹)	449	1.97 (0.30)
Trabecular thickness (μm)	449	76.1 (11.6)
Trabecular separation (mm)	449	0.44 (0.08)
Failure load (kN)	443	12.2 (2.2)

Values are given as mean (standard deviation, SD) unless otherwise specified. BMI = body mass index. vBMD = volumetric bone mineral density

Supplemental Table 8. Descriptive data of the HR-pQCT analyses in the radius in the MrOS Sweden cohort

	N	
Males, N (%)	367	367 (100)
Age (years)	367	79.8 (3.5)
BMI (kg/m ²)	367	25.9 (3.2)
Current smokers, N (%)	367	13 (3.5)
Cortical area (mm ²)	367	54.1 (17.9)
Cortical vBMD (mg/cm ³)	362	889 (52)
Cortical porosity (%)	362	4.3 (1.66)
Trabecular vBMD (mg/cm ³)	367	166 (38)
Trabecular number (mm ⁻¹)	367	2.06 (0.29)
Trabecular thickness (μm)	367	66.6 (10.5)
Trabecular separation (mm)	367	0.43 (0.09)
Failure load (kN)	364	4.7 (1.1)

Values are given as mean (standard deviation, SD) unless otherwise specified. BMI = body mass index. vBMD = volumetric bone mineral density

Supplemental Table 9. Association between serum valine levels and HR-pQCT parameters in the distal radius in a subsample of the MrOS Sweden cohort

	N	Beta (SE)	p-value
Cortical area (mm ²)	367	0.091 (0.051)	0.075
Cortical vBMD (mg/cm ³)	362	0.010 (0.054)	0.855
Cortical porosity (%)	362	0.084 (0.055)	0.129
Trabecular vBMD (mg/cm ³)	367	0.111 (0.053)	0.036
Trabecular number (mm ⁻¹)	367	0.073 (0.052)	0.163
Trabecular thickness (μm)	367	0.100 (0.052)	0.055
Trabecular separation (mm)	367	-0.091 (0.053)	0.085
Failure load (kN)	364	0.100 (0.052)	0.053

Linear regressions with serum valine as exposure and HR-pQCT parameters as outcome, adjusted for age, BMI, and current smoking. Beta values are given as standard deviation change of bone parameter per standard deviation increase of ln transformed valine.

Supplemental Table 10. Characteristics of the MrOS Sweden (Gothenburg) baseline data set

	MrOS baseline data set N = 969
Males, N (%)	969 (100%)
Age, years (SD)	75.2 (3.2)
BMI, kg/m ² (SD)	26.2 (3.5)
Current smokers, N (%)	76 (7.9)
Grip strength, kg	45.4 (8.0)
Femur neck BMD, g/cm ² (SD)	0.85 (0.14)

Values are given as mean (standard deviation, SD) or N (%). BMI = body mass index. BMD = bone mineral density.

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Supplemental Figure 1. Histograms of circulating valine levels. (A) untransformed arbitrary units and (B) natural logarithm transformed arbitrary units of circulating valine in the UK Biobank. n=111,230

Supplemental Figure 2. Correlations between amino acid levels. Pearson's correlation performed on natural log transformed amino acid levels in the UK Biobank